

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Monte Carlo method for the Spatially Homogenous Boltzmann equation

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Abstract.

This work presents a Monte Carlo computational approach for solving the spatially homogeneous nonlinear Boltzmann equation through a modified particle-in-cells model. Building upon the Belotserkovski and Yanitski and Kac models, the paper introduces a stochastic simulation scheme that synthesizes the principle of splitting operators with branching Markov processes. The method constructs unbiased estimators with small variance to compute molecular velocities and particle distributions, providing higher numerical accuracy and physical realism compared to traditional linear models. The developed algorithm enables efficient simulation of rarefied gas dynamics and demonstrates stable results across varying particle densities. Computational experiments, including shock wave structure modeling, show that this approach achieves improved convergence and fidelity in approximating spatially heterogeneous Boltzmann behavior.

Keywords: *Spatially Homogeneous Boltzmann equation, Particle-in-Cell Model, Branching Markov process, Monte Carlo Method, Unbiased Estimator, Conjugated Computational Schemes.*

Introduction

This paper studies and proposes statistical algorithms for solving the nonlinear integral Boltzmann equation in measures, which describes the physical processes of particle collisions and coalescence. The equations under consideration are one of the integral forms of the kinetic equations of rarefied gas dynamics. Markov processes with simple interactions are used to construct unbiased estimates for the solution of the kinetic equation of rarefied gas dynamics. The well-known relationship between nonlinear integral equations and branching Markov processes is exploited [1].

Recently, many studies have explored the application of the Monte Carlo method to solving such problems. The proposed computational scheme is analogous to the adjoint scheme in the linear case. The proposed scheme is examined in detail for the case of "rigid" molecules. To describe the scheme, it is convenient to switch from an equation in measures to an equation in densities. Various computational schemes are considered and their effectiveness compared. The resulting computational schemes are tested in solving a problem of shock wave structure. A statistical algorithm is proposed using the nonlinear spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation for the numerical implementation of the "particle-in-cell" statistical model, and methods for constructing unbiased, minimal-variance estimates for calculating the particle velocity in each cell are investigated.

Description of the Problem

Let us consider a nonlinear integral equation

$$F_t(dr, du) = F_0(dr - ut, du) \exp\{-H(r, u)t\} + \int_0^t \left[\exp\{-H(r, u)(t - s)\} \times \right. \\ \left. \times \iint_D T_{t-s}(dr, du; r_1, u_1, r_2, u_2) H(r_1, u_1) F_s(dr_1, du_1) F_s(dr_2, du_2) \right] . \quad (1)$$

where $(r, u) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^3$, $(r_i, u_i) \in D$, $i = 1, 2$, $t \in \mathbb{R}^1$. F_t and F_0 are measures in D , $H(r, u)$ is a non-negative function, $T_{t-s}(B, r_1, u_1, r_2, u_2)$ is a measurable function of the arguments (r_1, u_1, r_2, u_2) at fixed B , and at fixed (r_1, u_1, r_2, u_2) is a measure in D . The measures F_t , F_0 , T_{t-s} are considered non-negative.

Many works are dedicated to studying this kind of equation (for example [2]-[3]), where probabilistic features of solutions of this type of equation were studied. Equations of the type (1) represent one of the integral forms of kinetic equations for rarefied gas dynamics. The questions of existence and uniqueness of the solution of equation (1) were studied in [3,4]. It is known [3] that if F_0 and T_{t-s} are probabilistic measures and $H(r, u) < c = \text{const}$, then equation (1) has a unique nonnegative solution, which will be a probability measure. Existence and sub-stochasticity of the minimal nonnegative solution of equation (1) were also proven in [3].

In [2] authors constructively built a random process whose one-dimensional distribution satisfied equation (1). The advantages of this (unlike to problems mentioned above) allowed using a Monte Carlo method. This method of constructing unbiased estimators is a method of “direct modeling”. The advantage of the constructed computational scheme is that it permits estimating several functionals of the solution to equation (1) at one time. The disadvantage of this method is the difficulty constructing the random process that gives the minimal variance. Currently, this problem is not solved for that case. In the theory of Monte Carlo methods, there are methods (like “importance sampling”) that allow one to avoid these difficulties when solving concrete problems.

Below, for equation (1) we present construction methods for unbiased estimators for functionals of the type (h, f) , where $h(r, u, t)$ is a given function and $f(r, u, t)$ is a density of the measure F_t . The computational scheme that we derive here is an analogue of the conjugated scheme in the linear case. Furthermore, we will call this scheme a “conjugated scheme”. It is shown that the application of the results of Ermakov and others [2] allow the construction of a computational scheme with small variance, in particular, when prior information on the solution of equation (1) is known. When applying the above scheme to real physical problems, we must also show the statistical conservation of mass, impulse, and energy.

Construction of unbiased estimators

As is known, [5] among the statistical methods, which use Monte Carlo directly for modeling the flow of rarefied gas, the most efficient one is the statistical method of direct modeling of the nonstationary flow. In [6], they described a statistical “particle-in-cell” model, which was constructed based on the synthesis of ideas of splitting the

physical processes in each Δt . This method was used by Harlow [7], and in statistical interpretations by Berd [8] and Kac [9]. The specific of the “particle-in-cell” method are as the following. The state of every particle is characterized by vectors of coordinates and speeds u at a time $k\Delta t$, where $k = 0, 1, \dots$. A discrete random process

$$\{r(t), u(t)\} = \{r_1(t), u_1(t), \dots, r_N(t), u_N(t)\}$$

should be constructed in the heterogeneous coordinate space at each time $k\Delta t$. Here N is the number of molecules of monatomic gas in some volume D . The principle of splitting operator is used for constructing the random process $\{r(t), u(t)\}$.

The sampling divides into two steps. Monte Carlo method is used both for the numerical simulation of collisions of the particles in cells (the first step), as well as for the collision-free motion (free-molecular) of particles (the second step). For the numerical realization of the second step in [10] an algorithm is given, which does not require saving the corresponding spatial coordinates of the particles. For the numerical realization of the first step, spatially homogeneous model of Kac has been used. Thus, the synthesis of the ideas of splitting, and model of Kac has occurred. That gives rise to the Markov model, which approximates the Boltzmann equation with accuracy that depends statistically (condition of molecular chaos) on the number of particles. In [11], Yanitski explained the value of the principle of splitting.

The computational approach of Belotserkovski–Yanitski [6] is as efficient as the method of Berd, but has higher accuracy in approximating the Boltzmann equation. It is important to emphasize that “particle-in-cell” the statistical model of Belotserkovski–Yanitski is physically closer to the real problem.

As we propose yet another computational scheme, which directly uses the nonlinear spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation for the numerical realization of the first step in the “particles-in-cell” model of Belotserkovski–Yanitski. The method of constructing unbiased estimators with small variance is next given for calculating of a velocity of a single molecule $u(k\Delta t)$ for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

To find the velocity of the particle in each cell, we will use equation (1) in the spatially homogeneous case. In this case, equation (1) has the form

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\Delta t}(du) &= F_0(du) \exp\{-H(u)\Delta t\} + \int_0^{\Delta t} ds \exp\{-H(u)(\Delta t - s)\} \\ &\times \iint_D T_{\Delta t-s}(du; u_1, u_2) H(u_1) F_s(du_1) F_s(du_2). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $F_0(du)$, $F_{\Delta t}(du)$ are distribution particle velocity at time 0 and Δt respectively. Let $H(u) = c = \text{const}$. As is known [4], this equation has a unique positive solution that is a probabilistic measure, and the iterative method starting with $F_0(du) \exp\{-c\Delta t\}$ converges to the solution of equation (2). This is why we can apply the approach that was developed in [12] to equation (2). In [4], a direct computational scheme for solving equation (2) with certain side conditions was given. The results of [4] cannot be applied in our case, since the direct scheme, as given in [4], cannot estimate the value at the point (cell). In [4] a functional is estimated, not a point value.

Let us suppose that when the initial distribution, $F_0(du)$, has a density, the distribution $F_{\Delta t}(du)$ also has a density, $f(u, \Delta t)$. Making the transformation, which is analogous to the transformations [13], we obtain the following equation

$$\begin{aligned}
f(u, \Delta t) &= f(u, 0) \exp\{-ct\} + \int_0^{\Delta t} ds \int d\bar{\omega} \int du_c \\
&\times (1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\}) f_1(s) \frac{|u - u_c|}{c} f(u_c - |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s) f(u_c + |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s) \\
&\times \int_0^{\Delta t} ds \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} (1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\}) f_1(s) \left(1 - \frac{|u - u_c|}{c}\right) f(u, s) f(u_2, s) du_2.
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

For equation (3), we construct a branching Markov process, and thus we can derive various ‘‘conjugated’’ computational schemes for calculating an unbiased estimator of the functional (h, f) . Since $u = (u_x, u_y, u_z)$, we suppose $h(u, t) = u_x$, i.e. at time Δt , the velocity is computed by the following formula

$$U(\Delta t) = \int u_x f(u, \Delta t) du.$$

Now we describe the computational scheme. At time Δt , one particle is born with initial density $p_0(u)$ at the point $(u, \Delta t) = (u_x, u_y, u_z, \Delta t)$. Here, the estimator has the form

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) = \frac{u_x}{p_0(u)}.$$

Further, with probability $\alpha_0(\Delta t) = \exp\{-c\Delta t\}$, the particle is absorbed at the point $(u, \Delta t)$; here the estimator is computed by the formula

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) = \frac{u_x}{f(u, 0)}.$$

If the particle has not been absorbed, then the time $s_1 \in [0, \Delta t]$ is simulated with the probability density

$$f_1(s) = \frac{c \exp\{-c(\Delta t - s)\}}{1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\}}.$$

Then, with probability $\alpha_1(\Delta t) = \beta(1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\})$, where $\beta \in [0, 1]$, two particles will appear at the points $(u_c - |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s_1)$ and $(u_c + |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s_1)$. Here ω is an isotropic vector. The transition from u to u_c is done with the transition density $\psi_1(u_c)$. The density distribution at the point (u_c, s_1) , under the condition that collision has taken place (velocity changes), we write in the form of

$$P_1(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_c, s_1) = f_1(s) \psi_1(u_c).$$

Here the estimator is computed by the formula

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \rightarrow \zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \frac{2|u - u_c|}{\beta c} \psi_1(u_c).$$

Further, with probability $\alpha_2(\Delta t) = (1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\})(1 - \beta)$ two particles are created at the points (u, s_1) and (u_2, s_1) . Transition from u to u_2 is done with transition density $\psi_1(u_2)$. The density distribution of the point (u_2, s) with velocity remaining constant can be written in the form

$$P_2(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_2, s_1) = f_1(s) \psi_1(u_2).$$

In this case the estimator is computed by the formula

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \leftarrow \zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \left(1 - \frac{|u - u_2|}{c}\right) (1 - \beta)^{-1} (\psi_1(u_2))^{-1}.$$

Furthermore, new particles behave the same as the initial particle. Moreover, $s_0 = 0$, $s_k \in [0, t - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} s_i]$, $t < \sum_{i=0}^k s_i$, the moments of time s_k are chosen with probability density $f_1(s)$. At each step, the times s_1, s_2, \dots are chosen and the process finishes, when all particles are absorbed, or the condition

$$t - \sum s_i \leq \varepsilon,$$

where ε is a small number which was given beforehand, is satisfied.

Applying the results of [13] to equation (3), we derive the following assertion. If a process is given with an initial density

$$P_0(u, \Delta t) = \frac{|u_x f(u, \Delta t)|}{(|u_x|, |f(u, \Delta t)|)}.$$

the transition density

$$P_1(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_c, s_1) = f_1(s) \frac{2|u - u_c|c}{c} f(u_c - |u - u_c|, s) \frac{f(u_c + |u - u_c|, s)}{f(u, \Delta u)},$$

$$P_2(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_2, s_1) = f_1(s) \left(1 - \frac{|u - u_c|c}{c}\right) \frac{f(u, s) f(u_2, s)}{f(u, \Delta t)}.$$

and absorption probability

$$g(u, \Delta t) = \frac{f(u, 0)}{f(u, t)} \exp\{-c\Delta t\}.$$

then the variance of estimator $\zeta_{\Delta t}(u)$ will be the solution to equation (3).

Now, let us study the construction of unbiased estimators with small variance, using [14] and known data on the solution at $t \rightarrow \infty$. It's known [15] that as $t \rightarrow \infty$ the gas approaches the equilibrium state. Then features of the gas do not depend on spatial coordinates or time. In this case, the solution of equation (3) has the form (Maxwellian)

$$f(u) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{u^2}{2}\right). \quad (4)$$

For large t , the solution of our problem is close to (4). If we put (4) into expressions for P_1 and P_2 , this determines a Markov process. And gives us to use the small variance estimator $\zeta_{\Delta t}(u)$. The density distribution of the point (u_c, s_1) , when collision has taken place. When particle velocities change, has the form

$$\tilde{P}_1(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_c, s) = f_1(s) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-u_c^2 + |u - u_c|^2 + \frac{u^2}{2}\right).$$

If we make a change of variables in the following way: $\tilde{v} = 2v = 2(u_c - u)$, then we get for

$$\tilde{P}_1\left(u, \Delta t \rightarrow \frac{\tilde{v}}{2} + u, s_1\right) = f_1(s) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\tilde{v} - u)^2}{2}\right). \quad (5)$$

and for the point (u_2, s_1) , the collision has taken place (case of constant velocity) and the expression for the density distribution \tilde{P}_2 can be written as

$$\tilde{P}_2(u, \Delta t \rightarrow u_2, s_1) = f_1(s) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{u_2^2}{2}\right). \quad (6)$$

here

$$g(u, \Delta t) = \exp\{-c\Delta t\}. \quad (7)$$

Thus, velocities \tilde{v} and u_2 are distributed according to a normal law with densities

$$\psi_1(\tilde{v}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\tilde{v} - u)^2}{2}\right), \quad \psi_2(u_2) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{u_2^2}{2}\right),$$

and the optimal transition densities have the form (5), (6), (7).

For the construction of this algorithm, which is connected with densities (5), (6), (7), it is more convenient to apply equation (3), after the following change of variables

$$f(u, t) = \frac{1}{2} \psi(u) \varphi(u, \Delta t).$$

Here $\psi(u)$ is a known function, which is defined by (4). The computational scheme is simple. Because in computing the estimators there is no need to use weights that are larger than ours. Thus for (3) we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(u, \Delta t) &= \varphi(u, 0) \exp\{-c\Delta t\} + \int_0^{\Delta t} ds \int d\bar{\omega} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} du_c (1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\}) \\ &\quad \times f_1(s) \frac{2|u - u_c|}{2c} \frac{\psi(u_c - |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}) \psi(u_c + |u - u_c|\bar{\omega})}{\psi(u)} \\ &\quad \times \varphi(u_c - |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s) \varphi(u_c + |u - u_c|\bar{\omega}, s) \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\Delta t} ds \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} du_2 (1 - \exp\{-c\Delta t\}) f_1(s) \left(1 - \frac{|u - u_c|}{c}\right) \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{2} \frac{\psi(u)\psi(u_2)}{\psi(u)} \varphi(u, s) \varphi(u_2, s). \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $u_c = u + \frac{\tilde{v}}{2}$. The algorithm for constructing the unbiased estimator

$$U(\Delta t) = \int u_x f(u, \Delta t) du$$

is described as follows.

At time Δt , one particle with initial density $p_0(u)$ at the point $(u, \Delta t) = (u_x, u_y, u_z, \Delta t)$ appears. The particle at the point $(u, \Delta t)$ has a statistical "weight", which is equal to

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) = \frac{u_x}{p_0(u)}.$$

Furthermore, at the point $(u, \Delta t)$ the unbiased estimator $\zeta_{\Delta t}(u)$ is constructed for equation (6.26) in the following way. With probability

$$g(u, \Delta t) = \exp\{-c\Delta t\},$$

the particle is absorbed at the point $(u, \Delta t)$. The estimator is computed by the formula

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \leftarrow \varphi(u, 0) \zeta_{\Delta t}(u).$$

If the particle has not been absorbed, the time $s_1 \in [0, \Delta t]$ is simulated with probability density $f_1(s)$. Then, with probability

$$\frac{1 - g(u, \Delta t)}{2},$$

two particles appear at points

$$\left(\frac{\tilde{v}}{2} + u + \frac{\tilde{v}}{2}\bar{\omega}, s_1\right) \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{\tilde{v}}{2} + u - \frac{\tilde{v}}{2}\bar{\omega}, s_1\right).$$

Here the vector $\tilde{v} = u + \eta$, where η is sampled from a standard normal distribution. Here the estimator is computed by

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \leftarrow \frac{\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) |\tilde{v}|}{8c}.$$

Furthermore, with probability

$$\frac{1 - g(u, \Delta t)}{2},$$

two particles appear at the points (u, s_1) and (u_2, s_1) . Here the vector u_2 is sampled from a standard normal distribution. In this case, the estimator is computed as

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \leftarrow \zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \left(1 - \frac{|u - u_c|}{c}\right).$$

New particles behave the same as the original particles. The process finishes when all particles are absorbed, or when

$$\Delta t - \sum s_i \leq \varepsilon.$$

When the process completes, the estimator $\zeta_{\Delta t}(u)$ is multiplied by a value of function $\frac{1}{2}\psi(u)$ at the point $(u, \Delta t)$, i.e.

$$\zeta_{\Delta t}(u) \leftarrow \frac{\zeta_{\Delta t}(u)\psi(u)}{2}.$$

Thus, in each cell we compute the velocity at each time $k\Delta t$, where $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

Computational experiment and conclusions

As is known, the nonlinear Boltzmann equation describes the behavior of rarefied gas much better than the linear Kac model. This is why we can expect that application of the nonlinear spatially homogeneous Boltzmann equation in the ‘‘particles-in-cell’’ model

allows us to do a computation, which gives a more exact approximation to the spatially heterogeneous Boltzmann equation.

We underline that boundary conditions at infinity can be taken into consideration by the method [6]. There computations show that the results of modeling are similar with known [5] solutions of the Boltzmann equation. As an example, computations for the wave shock structure have been done.

Figure 1. The calculated profile of density and velocity

In the figure the Mach number is $M = 2$. The confidence level is 97%. The calculation were made with the following parameters. The number of particles in cells is $N_1 = 8$. The ratio $\Delta t/\Delta r_x$, where $\Delta r = (\Delta r_x, \Delta r_y, \Delta r_z)$, is chosen for numerical stability. The parameters for the problem are the following:

$$t = 2, \quad \Delta r_x = \Delta r_y = \Delta r_z = 0.2, \quad \lambda = 1.$$

We note that in interval, where the Boltzmann equations “work” (intermediate interval), the “particle-in-cell” statistical model approximates the spatially heterogeneous Boltzmann equation better. At the same time, this approximation is independent of the number of particles in D (even if a volume will only have one particle).

As a conclusion, first we note that for equation (3) we could apply an iterative process. For the computation of the integrals, which are obtained in the first and the second iteration, we can directly apply the Monte Carlo method. When comparing the density profiles at the first and the second iterations, we noticed very little bias. This can be explained by the fact that the iteration process to (3) converges slowly.

The second, gas dynamics problems can serve as examples of problems whose solution requires the use of modern multiprocessor computers. In particular, the multidimensional Boltzmann equation requires such technology for its solution. The complex nature of the kernel of this equation and the dependence of the solution on many variables necessitated the use of the Monte Carlo method. This method, as is well known, is particularly convenient for multiprocessor computers and allows for natural parallelization. Above, we describe an algorithm for solving the initial-boundary value problem for the Boltzmann equation, which could be effectively implemented on parallel computing systems.

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